

Ilokano Funny Phrases and Axioms as a Form of Entertainment

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Abstract

The research was conducted to identify Ilokano Funny phrases and Axioms. It was reflected that this is their form of entertainment in social media hence it was connected with their cultures and traditions as Ilokano. Among Ilokano in Isabela it was shown that what they post is merely an observation of real life what they've experienced hence this funny phrases and axioms is evidence they love and care among individual consciousness and to be aware of the post as if it you felt. The researcher first made a survey method using the purposive sampling technique in gathering Ilokano Funny Phrases and Axioms in social media. The data were gathered by means of a print screen using PC and cellphone. Based on the result of the research conducted: Entertaining oneself through social networking site is part of Ilokano life if your post is felt by somebody who read it that means you are affected in his or her post such as the Ilokano funny phrases Awan pakikibiyangak no haan nak kayat. Haan ka met nga kayat isunga agtalna ka! This post means mind your own business Ilokano believed that no matter how you idolized a man if you do not love each other it's useless therefore you must do nothing. The impact and reflections of axioms that were believed in by the Ilokano are the following: Be Thankful Always, God has a purpose, Be Happy and spread positivity this proof that Ilokano always view the positive side of our life.

Keywords: Axioms; Ilokano; Funny Phrases; and Entertainment, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the account of Luzano (2017) Ilokano is known for the research was conducted to identify the sayings that the Ilokano so much believed in; know what cultures and traditions are reflected in the Ilokano sayings; Based on the result of the research conducted: 1. The sayings that were so much believed in by the Ilokano are the following: A mature person always put his feet on the ground and foresee his next step (Ti tao nga ulbod madintu pulus mapagtalkan); Even it pours a gold of bars, if you are a lazy man, you could not pick anything at all (Uray agtudo ti balitok nu ti tao ket sadot madintu pulos makapidot; Iti utang mabayadan, ngem ti naimbag a nakem saan); A person who do not have debt of gratitude will never be successful in life (Ti dina ammo a taliawen ti naggapuanna, saan a makadanon ti papananna). 2. The cultures

and traditions that are reflected in these sayings are: not forgetting where he/she came from; being responsible; being industrious; more prudent towards other people; being helpful and unselfish; being thrifty; being honest; being respectful; and being hardworking. 3. The Ilokano sayings are being applied in their everyday life by practicing their culture and tradition freely. 4. The Ilokano sayings they so much believed in also become the basis of their honorable and progressive living.

1.1. Literature review / Theoretical background

According to Lincoln Barcon (2014) culture is defined as the language, beliefs, values, and norms that combine to make up the way of life of any society. The term civilization is similar, but not the same as culture. Civilization is used mostly to refer to the advanced way of life and the things that improve a society. Civilization is therefore, an improved form of culture. Culture on the other hand is any way of life: whether simple or complex. Based on the study of Shaira from Mindanao State University (2014) Sayings are powerful and word for thought of the people it gives lesson and guide in everyday living. In relations to the lecture series of Villafuerte (2000) Sayings is a short statement that gives justice, truth and has a basis of norms and values.

In the recent Timpuyog Dagiti Mannurat nga Iluko iti Filipinas Journal (April-May Edition 2017) and April 2018 Edition. Ilokano writers are given the opportunity to publish their articles written in Ilokano. On the article written by a prolific Ilokano writer *Mr. Crispin D. Dannug, Jr.* entitled "Saluad ti lenguahe ken kultura dagiti Ilokano" he mentioned the need to revitalize the Iloko language and the culture of the Ilokanos. Ilokano is spoken as a first language by some 7 million people, primarily in Northern Luzon specific in Cagayan Valley. It is also spoken as a second language by possibly another 2 million speakers in the northern areas of Luzon as a lingua franca in trade, commerce, and everyday communication. Many ethnic groups from the northern regions of the country are more proficient in Ilokano than in Tagalog, the national language. Nevertheless, at present, Ilokano remains a regional language with no official status. Its use in education is limited to the early elementary grades. Hence 54.20%, speaking Ilokano in the region.

1.2. Research questions

1. What are the common Ilokano funny phrases among Ilokanos?
2. What is the impact of Ilokano funny phrases?
3. What is their personal reflection in Ilokano Funny Phrases?

2. Method

Semiotic approaches or screenshot that is adapted of selected post in social media particularly in Facebook from Agasem That... official Facebook page and Ilokano Funny Phrases.

This research paper examine the acceptability and impact of each statement posts and share by their friends if it is a way of past time or showing sentiment in a particular event in their life.

This study provides a wider scope since the main instrument is the social networking site it was expected different point of view therefore researcher carefully planned and analyze each face back vice versa per comment of the netizens use.

2.1. Sample / Participants

Public Post from the official Facebook account of the two (2) page are the main source of respondents. A total of 218 respondents in a purposive sampling technique used in the research.

2.2. Instrument(s)

In order to analyze the data gathered for this study, the researchers made use of frequency counts and semiotic approaches in their post.

2.3. Data collection procedures

After the permission is granted, the researcher undertook the following steps:

1. Coordinate with the administration in Ilokano Funny Phrases and Agasem that...page.
2. By means of print screen or screen shots in their statement that was categorize as funny one the researcher captured it;
3. The netizens in that group posts and share their feeling or emotions in that particular arena of the user of account;
4. Compute, tabulate, analyze, and interpret the data gathered to arrive at the findings of the study.

2.4. Data analysis

In order to determine the ILOKANO FUNNY PHRASES AS A FORM OF ENTERTAINMENT the researcher has done purely a qualitative research.

SELECTED AXIOMS OF ILOKANOS

1. "AGKUPAS TI NAPINTAS A RUPA AGBALIW MET TI NAPINTAS A PAMMAGI NGEM DIN TO AG KUPAS TI BABAE NGA ADDAAN ITI NAPINTAS A UGALI"

We don't need to change our face our body or our physical appearance we just need to be the true we are. We don't need make up, lipstick, and different cosmetics. Although, we can change our physical appearance that cosmetics can change our behaviour. Because, what is beauty if you have negative attitude, what is sexy body if, you have bad deeds. It's better to be ugly if you have a good deeds, and if you have a clean heart. Being ugly is not bad, doing wrong doing is bad one. According to that line, a face can change but character cannot. But, it depends to the people who had this character, because there are people changing his/her attitudes. And they where afraid in the Lord so, they hide because of what they've done. We all knows that this line we can relate, do not make bad things, if you didn't want to shame to shame to the other people or God. That was just the one of the thousand example.

Being good is makes you beautiful, then making bad doing makes you ugly.

2. Nu Agtudo, Matudwan Amin a Tao (Gifts Must Be Given To all)

Blessing is the biggest things that we accept in our life that came from our Almighty God. Like our life, good health, and most important is our family. A family were in we are getting strength to overcome many challenges that we encountered.

And all things that we have is the reason why we inspired, inspired to do our obligation for our self, family and for our country. but why other people treated us unfairly? I think because of their power. a power to get what they want though they know that we need to be fair for others so what we need to do? We need to treat everyone as a family, a family who helping each other to built a good family as a whole. But why we experiencing challenges, I think because of our self and because of the others. Our self because we are the one who need to work hard so that we experience a good life others because sometimes they are the one who making ourselves down. But we don't need to be affected because the only key to success is our self not the others.so a blessing in our life is not just a small thing because all things that we have now and all things that we feel now is a blessing.

So what we need to do? We need to be fair for everything so that all people must give gifts or blessings. Not only a person who have a power to get what they want. So remember all people is born to be fair not to be unfair.

Be Thankful Always, God has a purpose

3. No maparagsak ka, ket pagragsakak met.

If i make you happy im happy too. You make me smile the way you smile without you im not complete that is the explanation for that this phrase it gives inspirations to others to do something simple to make people happy. Like if you are in love you will do everything you will give your best to makes your prince/princess happy.

Be Happy and spread positivity.

4. No trabaho, Gulpien, No kanen, In-inutem.

This means that we need to economize because it is hard to find another work. We need to do that because our life is just poor only its' hard to find money to buy all your needs. In this scenario we don't waste the time to work just do what you want and you must buy all your needs. Its means that don't be arrogant we need to more on working than to spending. We need to serve or save money for the future. We have or its better to get excite on working than spending. Some people are more on spending than working. Those people who are not thinking for their future are sometimes called "one day millionaire". If it's work, do it fast. If it's food, eat it little by little. They said time is gold, when you work, do it fast. Do your work with your best. Do it fast so that it will finish early. Do it fast so that their is time for the other. Just manage your time. Don't waste your time. On the other hand, if it is food, eat it little by little. It says that when you eat, don't be so fast. Let's eat normally. It is better to eat slowly than to eat so fast because that is bad for your or our health. I know that everyone of us wants or like to eat all the time. And that's what Filipino is. When we see some foods, we are craving because we want that food or we are hungry. But at the sayings says, eat it little by little so you will become more healthy.

Be Accountable of everything happen in your life.

5. AWAN TI MASULEK NGA MADI AGIVA

Accidental part on the eye makes everyday cry. It means no one can get angry when you made not good for them. All people should felt angry when we made not good for them. I think they made this phrase for those people who don't know what other people feel when they made not good. Or they don't know what will be the feeling of these people recieved not good words.

You can't Please Everyone!

6. Awán kas iti sursúro a sanikuá, ta daytá awán makatákaw kenká.

Knowledge is wealth that can't be stolen.

Education is Knowledge. Education is the process where an individual learns information so that he/she can use it to enhance his/her abilities for his/her future.

It answers all the questions that we have. It enhances our skills. It also tells us about our past and its story. Most importantly, it is our valued treasure.

This treasure is the only thing in our life that cannot be stolen. Our parents spend a lot of money for us to be educated and they know that it is all worth it.

When we die, we cannot bring all the earthly things in Heaven, but I believe that we can bring what we have learned while we are still on earth. We should share to other people the knowledge that we have learned so that they can also share it to the generations to come.

Education is indeed the most precious treasure that any of us can have. Once we have been educated, it is now up to us how we will use and treasure it. It needs a lot of perseverance and concentration so that we can be educated.

It will take us lots of time to develop our skills, which are all part of achieving god education. If we have been educated, it is not impossible to reach our goals, dreams and ambitions in life.

Education does not have any hindrances as long as we are willing and eager to learn and give our attention to it. We need to sacrifice a lot and keep in our minds that it is for our own good and for our future.

We need to have goals, dreams and ambitions in life so as not to waste our time in not so important things.

As long as we are willing to pursue our dreams, it is not impossible to reach it. There are lots of options for us to choose from and all we have to do is to work hard, sincerely and seriously.

We need to work hard so that we can mold ourselves into competitive and knowledgeable individuals in the future. Money should not be an issue for this matter because it is your will that counts which help you predict your own future.

We must remember that education is the most precious gift that one could ever have. Education is the only treasure that cannot be stolen from us.

Knowledge is Power. One who has the right knowledge and works hard and smart will be successful in any task. Knowledge gives us the ability to think in all the ways. A person with Knowledge can solve a problem easily than with a person without knowledge.

Knowledge is Wealth. If a person thinks money can rule the world, the person is definitely wrong. To conquer the world, Knowledge is very important.

Knowledge is the path of wisdom; Knowledge helps us to differentiate between good and bad; right and wrong; worthy and unworthy. Only when a person is educated, he/she gets the ability to judge a situation. To overcome any problem, Knowledge is significant.

We all would have heard this saying in many places "Give a man a fish, he will eat one day; Teach a man how to fish he will eat every day". This is a very true saying that applies to everyone's life.

There is no best help than helping a person to enhance knowledge. If we have money, we can make a living. But if we are enriched with knowledge, we can make money ourselves. We can lead a great life if we have the power to tune our life ourselves through the knowledge we gained.

Educating ourselves alone is not enough; emphasizing the importance of knowledge to the society is quite essential. We should think about the goodness of the whole society. We should empower the minds of young students through motivations we give to them. Creating awareness on the importance of knowledge over everything is the need of the hour. Knowledge is the biggest wealth in life.

The most powerful weapon in this world is Knowledge. Great men have conquered and ruled the world with their Knowledge. We would have heard the saying "Pen is Mightier than Sword". War can break worlds but a wise decision that comes through the knowledge of a person can bring in peace without loss.

Knowledge is very important for any person, be it rich or poor. A person is judged by his knowledge, not by his money or appearance. A person who has skill and knowledge wins the race any day. So it is good to educate ourselves and motivate others to improve their knowledge so that the day to success is not far away. True that thieves cannot steel a person's knowledge. If the second part of the query is to know whether any research or inventions could be secured to avoid stealing, then the answer is that all researched products and inventions are patented and ownership registered.

Knowledge is unlimited you can take it free and share for the good of everybody.

7. Ti kamátis, di agbúnga ti manggá.

The tomato plant doesn't grow mangos. A good person doesn't come from a bad family because if you really come from a good family I believe you have been taught good morals and really brought you up.

Some people also come from a good family but do not listen to her parents' teaching and maybe they have influenced her to become a bad person. But when you come from a bad family does not mean that you are not too bad because not everyone

And then stop trying to have control over other people and over life in general. We sometimes fall victim to the illusion that we have control, but we really don't. Let go and accept that you can't control others or most of the world around you.

Everything is impermanent. Everything. And that's pretty scary. Thinking about it elicits fear in us (at least, it does in me). So when we're confronted with change, impermanence, and loss, we respond with resistance, and we attempt to gain or exert control over things.

Instead of resisting, we need to accept that change is the nature of life. We can't alter that, and there's no point in fighting it. Doing so will only cause us to suffer.

Letting go sounds so simple. However, it's anything but. These problems and patterns that I've reviewed can be deeply ingrained in us. And we tend to protect them and continually return to them, because in doing so we feel like we're protecting ourselves.

In order to let go, you need to dig down deep and realize that you don't need protection. You need to recognize and believe that you'll be okay - that everything will be okay.

If you're able to let go and start accepting things as they are instead of how you'd like them to be, you'll find that you'll suffer less from the problems of stress, emotional ties to the past or future, frustration with others, struggles with loss, and succumbing to fear.

By letting go, you'll set yourself free.

Letting go of things, whether it's your own choices and actions, events from your past or things said, is one of the biggest obstacles many people face when it comes to getting sober. Addiction is a terrible disease and when we're under its grasp, we often say and do horrible things, often to the people that mean the most to us.

When you're facing these actions and the things we've said in the cold light of sobriety, it can be extremely embarrassing or painful, which is a big reason learning to let those things go is important. The past is the past, and as much as we may wish otherwise, nothing that we do now can undo or change what we've done or said in that past.

When you learn to let go of those things, or let go of what others have done to you, you're giving yourself the chance to do better in the future. If we hold on to mistakes or the things that shame us, we're dwelling on them, not learning from them.

It's important to learn to acknowledge your actions and how you feel, but then you have to let it go to make room for bettering yourself. Learning from those mistakes and then pushing them out of mind will go a long way in helping you have a more steady sobriety, and by letting it go, you're loving yourself enough to let go rather than just let it fester in your mind.

Learning to let go of your past and your past mistakes is one of the best things you can do for your future and your recovery, and you may feel a physical release of tension once you truly begin to let go. Letting go makes room for the life you want to live in the future, not the one you left behind in addiction.

Love always win no matter how challenges attack us.

10. Saan uray inton kaano ibaga dayta kukuayo natan-ok, no dakayo aramiden awan pagraemen ken iti luma nga tattao.

Never say that you're a genius if you do not have respect to your older people. A genius is mostly never connected. A genius isn't always able to connect to everyone. There almost always is a social complex. Someone with a very high IQ would hardly be able to be comfortable with your general crowd. So, if you want to spot a genius, look for someone disconnected, but not with a look of void on their face. They'll be engrossed in something that is beyond the grasp of a regular individual. So in short, someone who exhibits the symptoms of being a dumb social outcast with a certain sharpness in their eyes, and a bit of spark in their behaviour. A genius may not always be able to relate to people and their humour as so rightly mentioned in the answer wiki. Well, the reason then again being the inability of the genius to perceive something mundane and routine as actually something mundane and routine. A genius person may seem like odd to some, but there is a reason behind their "madness." A genius tends to have really high intellect, is very creative, and engages in some odd behaviours.

Their high IQ is very beneficial to many things, people, and issues that need dealt with. Many geniuses have invented things that have changed the world, only to live life outside of the spotlight. This article explains the different signs and traits of someone who is a genius. Because of their high IQ, geniuses have a hard time connecting with people. They tend to keep to themselves due to other interests that the common population are not interested in. They don't often marry or have children, and don't fit in on the common social calendar. Geniuses also have a hard time conversing with others. Their mind tends to only speak as needed, instead of bantering or chatting. When they speak, it is about something very important. They may even suffer from a touch of social anxiety disorder, because they always feel like they don't "fit in." All geniuses seem to have developed the ability to concentrate single minded on one question, problem or goal at a time, and to exclude all other diversions or distractions. The more intensely you concentrate your thoughts and attention, and the more

intensely you are emotionally involved with a problem or goal, the more likely it is that your mind will respond with the kind of creative ideas that you need. And the good news is that concentration comes from practicing the process of concentrating whenever you have something you want to accomplish.

One of the best ways to develop this habit of concentration is to define your goal or problem clearly, in writing, at the top of a piece of paper. Then, write down every single detail that you can think of that pertains to that goal or problem. Write every fact, figure and piece of information that you have. The more you write, the more likely it is that you will come up with exactly the idea that you need to solve the problem or difficulty that is currently holding you back. A genius is that they have incredible problem solving skills and developed a systematic approach to solving problems. Usually, they write them down clearly on paper in advance. Accurate problem definition leads to a solution in fully 50% of cases. Most of the time, when you have a problem or series of problems that is causing you worry or concern, it is because you have not yet sat down and clearly defined exactly what the problem is. Most people who are unhappy in life have no goals. The very act of sitting down and writing out a list of goals will change your perspective completely. When you take your list of goals, organize it by priority and then make written plans to achieve your most important goals, your mind will start to sparkle with ideas that will help you.

Your negativity and pessimism will vanish. You will experience a surge of energy and enthusiasm and you will want to get up and get going immediately on whatever it is you have written down. There are an enormous number of things that you think you "know" about your life and situation that are simply not true. One of the best ways to manage your creativity is to carefully check and double check your facts and figures to be sure that they are accurate. Being a genius person have respect to everyone. A respectful person is the person who gain respect from others, they only knew how to give respect to others. So we should call them a respectful person. Respect is esteem for, or a sense of the worth or excellence of, a person, a personal quality, ability, or a manifestation of a personal quality or ability. So says most dictionaries; but it goes far deeper than that. Respect is one of those words that can take on various meanings depending on its use both in speech and perception.

The more learning we have the more reflection is an evident expression of humbleness.

Ilokano

SELECTED ILOKANO FUNNY PHRASES

Online Posts in Facebook	Impact, Reflection and Message
1. Basta naka brace kanu ket kyut, anya itti makunam kailian.	This means that anyone who place braces in their teeth is cute and beautiful in the eyes of the beholder. The words "kanu" means "daw or maybe" it means there is no assurance in one thing "makunam" means "suggestions or opinions" for the netizens its' not good used or placed a brace because its' not pleasing to them but for the real person who used braces its' just a normal way to arrange dislocate and excess teeth.
2. Datay pudno ammom met lang kadi ti agluto.	This type of ilokano funny phrases attack the lazy people among Ilokanos youth.
3. No naka-idda ak,FLAT met ti tiyan ko. Ngem no nag-sikig akon, ayna!!! Kunam la no 8 nga bulan toy Sikog kon.	For the netizens this reflect how big their stomach is. Their personal impact we should discipline ourselves in terms of eating.
3. Bes haan mo unay partakan magna baka maipadugmam ka.	The netizens view this as everybody has our own race in life wait for your time in that spot.
4. No Siak ti kumottong kunak to met! Who U Ka kenyak.	This imply that if you are sexy human wows you. In the eyes of human they view a person not on attitude one but also in physical appearance one.
5. Ber manen gayamen, kumusta daguita bilbil mo.	This represents holidays in Ilocoslovakia is represents foods and long vacation.
6. Kunam la no sinno nga Pastillas nga nagpudaw ti picture, iti Personal kasla ubet met ngayam ti Kaldero jay dalikan.	In common the netizens reflect this as we should be genuine always physically, spirituality, intellectuality and emotionally. Since Facebook is a virtual life the scenario of it sometimes hide it in actual way of living.
7. Ta rupam maidulin mot i filter, ngemta ugalim madi.	The netizens most common comments is be true to yourselves even others don't.
8. Kunada agruwaar kano daguita Tokak no matutudo. Apay ngay adda nakitak	This post has different meaning but according to the account of the owner sarcasm among his post to show awareness and self-reflection among his

agruprupa nga karag uray awan tudo.	friends.
9. Haan nga gapu ta haan da ka nga singsingiren ket madi ka agbayaden. Agbain ka met. Nangina bagas.	This reflects and has an impact that credit must pay at the right time and perfect place because time can talk and prices become elevating.
10. Basta manangisem, adda iduldulin na nga naalsem nga nalitem.	The netizens views this every smile has a a deep secrets a person have.
11. Awan ti Napitak nga pagnaan, nu palanitan ti papanam.	Netizens view this Ilokanos in terms of wedding is alert or active to attend even how hard the road is.
12. No matamaaan ka kadaguiti, patama da. Kayat na satwen aramid mo dayta.	As a whole their feedback is if you are guilty with their judgement and that is your works.
13. Sika ti nalaing agistorya, sika met ti ado aramid na.	Don't be a storyller if you yourselves has a lot of story that the world has shown
14. Diay gayyem mo nga puro malamot panpanunuten na.	This proved that friends with the same feathers' flock together because they have in common and that is food.
15. Samo lang mapanonot nga nagalas ngayam isuna nu nakamove-on kan!	Be self-reflectivist rather than escapist, you should know your limitation
16. Inaramid na ka lang nga kasla duggong! Edi naala na kan, Binilog-bilog naka laeng. Edi nauma isuna kanyamon, sana ka impaltiik paadayo ti biag na!	Don't be easily fall in love with a man who's personal needs has something in return so later on you can't repent at last be a success to somebody.
17. Kurang lang agllabosen, makaado lang ti Likes ti Garampang.	In their response to achieve beauties inside among your circle of friends don't wear negative and malicious cloth that changes your personality.
18. Sa mo met lang ibaga nga agpakuttong kan no nabsog kan.	Unexpected reaction when you are full eating be it's a matter of self-discipline and self-assessment.
19. Piman kakaisuna nga bunga ti marunggay nagpukaw pay.	Don't steal and fear God if it is not yours then do not get it.
20. Nalaaw ti lata no awan karga na. Kasla met kenka, awan siguro karga ta ulom isunga sumanao ka.	Empty can scatters everywhere, be a change if you hve contribute something then humble yourselves do not talk if your mouth is empty.
21. Mano aya sweldom dayta trabahom nga pagkachisoma.	Don't gossip your neighbourhood you cannot became rich if you do so.

22. Bumaket kan, padasem metten ti agsayet	Many people would scared if they saw their face in the mirror its not too late to experience love life.
23. Kabusor da ka ta appalan da ka! Lukdit yo kunam	Some people hate you not because who you are. Ignore them and proved them wrong.
24. Kasatno ka ngarod kumottong no lamot ka nga lamot.	If you want to be slim simply minimize eating a vice versa post from the netizens that people must controlled themselves in terms of food.
25. Nu madim ammo ti pudno nga istorya, agtalna ka! Samsampitaw.	Don't talk if you don't know the whole story because it can add, multiply, subtract and divide so better shut up.
26. Awan pakikibiyangak no haan nak kayat. Haan ka met nga kayat isunga agtalna ka!	Don't ever forget who was there for you when no one else was
27. Haan nga naragsak ti biag na, isunga dayta biag mot i paggatelan na!	Never announce your moves before you make them because our journey determines our destiny. Find a true friend that you can comfort for.
28. Feeling Blessed ngem puro utang.	Don't ever forget who was there for you when no one else was most specially your friends because credit is a credit a obligation to return back
29. No sinno pay ti sadot, isupay nalaing pumutot.	For the netizens observation, those who are lazy they are the one who has a lot of siblings.
30. No matamaan ka daguiti posts da aray kunam, nu haan mo kayat Aglisi ka.	A warning for everybody to balance our post in social media because some are aware and maybe are not.

3. Discussion and Recommendations

The Ilokano funny phrases and axioms are being useful in their everyday life and become the basis of their reflections, contribute impact in their personality and progressive living. This proved that Ilokanos is a funny yet witty in terms of their post in social media. The researcher also found out that this axioms and funny phrases can also integrate in school curriculum as Ilocano literature. The researcher found out that Ilokano Funny Phrases and Axioms is a form of entertainment among Ilokanos of Isabela Province they post on Facebook as leisure and another form of fun alike activity.

Based on the result of the research, the researcher is recommending for a deeper study on the following aspects:

- Inculcate in the minds of Ilokano students the axioms and ilokano funny phrases that deal about their culture in entertainment form;
- Revive, enrich and promote good ilokano funny phrases and axioms that will serve the youth as a reference in next generation;
- Give attention and essential roles of ilokano funny phrases and axioms identify the root of the seeds of wisdom that they teach to the life of the people;
- Provide a website that ilokanos can easily accessible ilokano funny phrases and axioms that those fan of reading it is locally a native ilokano;
- Broadcast the result of the study among Ilocoslovakia region for them to evaluate and make some critique with this research.

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